

Species	Species Code	Family	Scientific Name	Riparian Wash East		Willow Woodland		Marsh to Upland	Bridge Wash West	Bridge Wash East	Remnant Mixed Riparian	Riparian Wash East	Bridge Wash East	Remnant Mixed Riparian
				SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	SC7	SC8	SC9	SC10	SC11
Carnivora														
Coyote	CAFA	Canidae	<i>Canis latrans</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.021	0.183	0.290	0.316	0.000	0.043	0.068
Fox Species (Grey Fox, Desert Kit Fox*)	FXSP	Canidae	<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus, Vulpes macrotis*</i>	0.013	0.362	0.138	0.032	0.011	0.011	0.145	0.092	0.027	0.000	0.000
Mountain Lion	PUCO	Felidae	<i>Puma concolor</i>	0.039	0.053	0.064	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.013	0.026	0.176	0.014	0.014
Bobcat	LYRU	Felidae	<i>Lynx rufus</i>	0.066	0.245	0.032	0.021	0.021	0.086	0.303	0.263	0.000	0.214	0.230
Ungulata														
Mule Deer	ODHE	Cervidae	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	0.684	0.000	0.213	0.117	0.021	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Rodentia														
Rabbit Species (Black-tailed Jack Rabbit, Desert Cottontail)	RASP	Leporidae	<i>Lepus californicus, Sylvilagus audubonii</i>	0.026	0.255	0.319	0.064	0.000	0.194	0.658	0.513	0.000	0.729	0.729
Skunk Species (Striped Skunk, Spotted Skunk)	SKSP	Mephitidae	<i>Mephitis mephitis, Spilogale putorius</i>	0.461	0.372	0.234	0.053	0.011	0.022	0.013	0.000	0.014	0.000	0.000
Squirrel Species (White-tailed Antelope Squirrel*, California Ground Squirrel, Round-tailed Ground Squirrel*)	SQSP	Sciuridae	<i>Ammospermophilus leucurus*, Otospermophilus beecheyi, Xerospermophilus tereticaudus*</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.043	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.014	0.041
Rats and Mice Species (Canyon Mouse*, Desert Pocket Mouse*, Little Pocket Mouse*, Long-tailed Pocket Mouse*, San Diego Pocket Mouse*, Cactus Mouse*, Desert Deer Mouse*, Spiny Pocket Mouse*, California Pocket Mouse*, Desert Kangaroo Rat*, Merriam's Kangaroo Rat*, White-Throated Woodrat*, Bryant's Woodrat*, Southern Grasshopper Mouse*)	RMSP	Heteromyidae, Muridae, Cricetidae	<i>Peromyscus crinitus*, Chaetodipus penicillatus*, Perognathus longimembris*, Chaetodipus formosus*, Chaetodipus fallax*, Peromyscus eremicus*, Peromyscus maniculatus sonoriensis*, Chaetodipus spinatus*, Peromyscus californicus*, Dipodomys deserti*, Dipodomys merriami*, Neotoma albigula venusta*, Neotoma lepida*</i>	0.000	0.596	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.032	0.013	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.122

Note:

Asterisk (*) next to species indicates that those species could not be identified by camera images, but have ranges that occur in this area.

Table 1. Species list and the relative abundance indices of each species at each location across Sentenac Cienega

Figure 1. Bar graph of the relative abundance indices for each species across all camera locations, categorized into zone

Figure 2. Map of the relative abundance index of all camera locations in Sentenac Cienega, categorized into zones

Figure 3. Pie chart of the total sum of species across all camera locations in Sentenac Cienega.

Figure 4. Animal species richness across the eleven locations in Sentenac Cienega.